

SCIANCE

D6.4

Data Management Plan

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Abstract

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The Data Management Plan for the SCIANCE project focuses on data collection, usage and sharing activities within the project. It also describes how data is protected, made accessible and available according to existing regulations and the project's Grant Agreement. The deliverable comprises a Data Summary, a section dedicated to Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability and addresses Data Security and ethical aspects. The Data Management Plan addresses current provisions for data management and will be updated regularly to reflect any changes that might arise.

Revision History

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Author(s)	Roberto Trasarti (Centro Nazionale delle Ricerche, CNR) Marco Braghieri (Centro Nazionale delle Ricerche, CNR) Roberta Savella (Centro Nazionale delle Ricerche, CNR)		
Reviewer(s)	Natalia Manola (OpenAIRE)		
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Terminology / Acronyms

EC	European Community
EU	European Union
DMP	Data Management Plan
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
CSA	Coordination and Support Action

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1 Executive summary

This document is Deliverable 6.4 (Data Management Plan) under Task 6.4 (Ethics, Inclusion and Data Management) developed by Work Package 6 (Coordination I) of the SCIANCE project, funded by the European Union (Grant Agreement number 101293570).

According to the European Commission Horizon Europe HE program [guide](#) (v 5.1, published on 15 September 2025), the Data Management Plan is “a cornerstone for responsible management of research outputs, notably data and are mandatory in Horizon Europe for projects generating and/or reusing data”. Moreover, the program guide underlines DMPs as “formal documents that outline from the start of the project all aspects of the research data lifecycle, which includes its organisation and curation, and adequate provisions for its access, preservation, sharing, and eventual deletion, both during and after a project”.

All the project's data and metadata will be managed in line with FAIR principles of “Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability” and under the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”, under conditions outlined in the GA.

The DMP will be a living document, updated according to necessity and ahead of each periodic review. According to the European Commission Horizon Europe HE program [guide](#) (v 5.1, published on 15 September 2025), “a good practice regarding DMPs is to register them as non-restricted public deliverables to make them openly accessible, unless legitimate reasons exist to keep them confidential”.

The European Commission provides a [template](#) for DMP which will be followed in this deliverable.

2 Data summary

SCIANCE’s DMP will align with FAIR research data principles, comply with GDPR, IPR and other applicable regulations. While, according to the Grant Agreement Annex 1 Part B, “the SCIANCE project is expected to generate a limited number of data outputs, mostly related to consultation and reporting activities” due to its nature as a CSA (Coordination and Support Action) project, the DMP will be continuously updated to reflect any necessary adjustments.

As per Grant Agreement Annex 1 Part A, the DMP will also “explicitly acknowledge the collection and processing of limited personal information (e.g. names, institutional affiliations, contact details) required for the organisation of workshops and feedback consultations. Such data will be used exclusively to manage invitations, attendance, and follow-up communications, including structured feedback collection. All personal information will be processed in full compliance with GDPR and partner institutional policies, stored securely with access restricted to authorised staff, and deleted once its purpose has been fulfilled. Only anonymised and aggregated feedback will be retained for reporting and evaluation, with no personal data shared beyond the consortium”.

Research data generated during the project, expected to be integrated into the RAISE Digital Hub, include:

- A comprehensive knowledge base containing systematic state-of-the-art reviews on AI-enabled scientific research in the pilot scientific areas, and on cross-cutting AI for Science research and innovations.
- A European AI in Science infrastructure directory.
- A registry of validated good practices on AI-enabled scientific research.
- Reports on consultations and participatory processes methodologies followed to co-create research and innovation priorities and develop infrastructure upgrade scenarios and cooperation mechanisms.
- Documents detailing evidence-based scenarios for European AI in Science infrastructure development, including feasibility assessments, investment priorities, and implementation pathways for enhanced resource coordination.
- An endorsed implementation roadmap produced in Phase 3 of the project through feasibility testing of infrastructure and coordination scenarios.
- A document integrating the knowledge base and the co-designed research priorities (produced in Phase 1 and Phase 2 of the project) into a Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda for AI in Science.
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3 FAIR Data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

In this section, the EC DMP template requires to address if data will be identified with a persistent identifier, which metadata will be created and provided to allow discovery. Moreover, the EC DMP template asks to address the creation of keywords provided in the metadata to optimise the possibility for discovery, harvest, and index.

Currently, the SCIANCE project envisions the publication of reports and consultation reports within non-restricted public deliverables which will be rendered accessible openly online. A tag system will be utilised to increase findability and allow for a more flexible use. In case of the generation of surveys, no confidential information (as detailed in Section 2) will be shared while anonymised and aggregated feedback will be retained for reporting and evaluation.

The project has activated a [community-dedicated page](#) on [Zenodo](#), “a multi-disciplinary open research repository hosted by CERN and commissioned by the European Commission through the OpenAIRE project to support the Open Data and Open Access movements in Europe”.

3.2 Making data accessible

3.2.1 Repository

In this section, the EC DMP template asks to address matters regarding data repository. At present, for internal documents and working documents shared among the partners, the SCIANCE project is utilising Microsoft [SharePoint](#), “a web-based collaboration and document management platform used by organizations to store,

organize, share, and access information securely”. As the project progresses and the RAISE Digital Hub will become active, the DMP will be modified accordingly. The platform is currently administered by project partner ESF.

Figure 1: Screenshot of the SCIANCE repository

The SCIANCE SharePoint currently requires a two-step [verification](#) to sign in: “two-step verification (sometimes called multi-factor authentication) helps protect you by making it more difficult for someone else to sign in to your Microsoft account. It uses two different forms of identity: your password, and a contact method (also known as security info)”. Thus, access is restricted to authorised contacts. When consultations with experts take place, SharePoint will be used to allow the experts to share working documents among themselves. Only the experts specifically authorised by the partners for the consultations will have access to the working documents.

As specified in the Grant Agreement Annex 1 Part A, one of the tasks of WP8 will be to establish the RAISE Digital Hub, which will provide structured, interactive access to SCIANCE outputs at different stages of development, including pilot results, SRIA, roadmaps, training materials, and good practices, while also referencing relevant information from existing platforms such as AI-on-Demand, AI4EOSC, GenAI Hub, EOSC nodes, and Dataspaces.

3.2.2 Data

In this section, the EC DMP template asks to address matters regarding data. The Grant Agreement envisions SCIANCE outputs to include “deliverables, reports, guidelines, communication and dissemination materials, training resources, software, and datasets”. At this stage, the project does not envision the generation of datasets containing personal data or anonymized data, due to its nature as a CSA (Coordination and Support Action) project. Should dataset generation be required, all data collection and processing will be conducted in compliance with the GDPR, applicable legislation, and relevant EU ethical guidelines.

The project will not develop AI but uses AI technologies with the [OpenAIRE](#) graph and LLMs for qualitative coding. Moreover, the use of AI models will follow the European Commission guidelines:

- [Living guidelines on the responsible use of generative AI in research](#)
- [Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI](#)

3.2.3 Metadata

In this section, the EC DMP template asks to address matters regarding metadata. The metadata generated by the SCIANCE project will adhere to metadata standards and best practices to ensure that the research data produced during the project will be open and FAIR.

3.3 Making data interoperable

To render data and metadata in line with FAIR principles, standards and formats will be chosen to increase “Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability” and under the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”, under conditions outlined in the GA.

3.4 Increase data re-use

According to the GA, “the SCIANCE project is expected to generate a limited number of data outputs, mostly related to consultation and reporting activities”.

At present the SCIANCE project envisions limited data re-use to data collection activities connected with personal data. This data will be used strictly in connection with the management of invitation, attendance, and follow-up communication, including structured feedback communication.

The project’s activity will be available in the form of reports and consultation reports within non-restricted public deliverables. The RAISE Digital Hub, once established, will ensure structured, interactive access to SCIANCE outputs at different stages of development.

4 Other research outputs

In case of collection, usage, or generation of other research outputs of digital nature (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.), these will be stored leveraging project partners research infrastructures, such as [SoBigData](#). SoBigData is “a European open science research infrastructure for social mining”. SoBigData RI has a catalogue system that “promotes responsible and ethical data use by providing metadata, documentation, and access conditions aligned with privacy and legal requirements. It enables discovery, reuse, and comparison of resources across disciplines. By fostering openness, interoperability, and reproducibility, the SoBigData [Catalogue](#) helps transform large-scale digital traces into actionable scientific and societal insights”.

5 Allocation of Resources

Data management in the SCIANCE project is placed under the remit of Work Packages 6 and 7 (Coordination I and Coordination II). A specific task (6.4 and 7.4) named Ethics, Inclusion and Data Management, focuses on the activities regarding the creation and maintenance of the Data Management Plan, which will be compliant with GDPR, IPR and other applicable regulations and ethical guidelines. The DMP will undergo period reviews and updates. CNR is task lead on both Task 6.4 and 7.4 and as such will liaise directly with the project management regarding the DMP.

Where needed long-term preservation will be actioned leveraging project partner RI, such as SoBigData Research Infrastructure (see Section 3).

6 Data Security

Data security is currently addressed by the adoption of Microsoft SharePoint, administered by project partner ESF. Access is restricted to authorised users, which must log in using a two-factor verification procedure.

All personal data collected by the project, connected to workshop or consulting activities, will be managed and stored in compliance with GDPR, other relevant European and national legislation and project partner institutional policies.

7 Ethics

7.1 Ethical aspects of data management

As described in this DMP, the project will follow the FAIR principles of good research data management and the approach of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.

Data sharing, where necessary, will be compliant with GDPR and relevant national legislation and project partner institutional policies. Data processing will be guided by data minimisation principle and personal data will be processed “to the extent necessary to implement project activities and ensure compliance with the Grant Agreement” as per as per GA Annex 1 Description of the Action section B. In case of collection of personal data, which is currently envisioned to be limited to:

- Names
- Institutional affiliations
- Contact details

Informed consent will be included. However, “only anonymised and aggregated feedback will be retained for reporting and evaluation, with no personal data shared beyond the consortium” as per GA Annex 1 Description of the Action section B.

As described in the GA Annex 1 Part B, participation in all project activities, including consultations, sessions, workshops, interviews, etc. will be on a voluntary basis, with participants recruited solely in the basis of their expert capacity to provide input, and based on their professional profile, i.e., the project does not involve profiling of individuals, recruitment of participants as research subjects to be studied, and negligible risk of ethically problematic unexpected findings.

7.2 Use of AI systems for project’s activities

The use of AI systems during the project will be strictly monitored and documented to ensure adherence to the key ethical principles of:

- Reliability in ensuring the quality of research
- Honesty in developing, carrying out, reviewing, reporting and communicating on research transparently, fairly, thoroughly, and impartially
- Respect for colleagues, research participants, research subjects, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage, and the environment
- Accountability for the research from idea to publication,

as described in the Living guidelines on the responsible use of generative AI in [research](#), based on the [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) and the work of the [High-Level Expert Group on AI](#).

To ensure accountability, project partners will document when Large Language Models will be used in their research activity (for example for text summarization) and this will be clearly noted in the research outputs.

To ensure the quality of research, with particular attention to its accuracy, when AI systems will be used their results will be reviewed by human researchers.

If AI systems will be used to register and transcribe meetings and consultations, the participant will be informed prior to the beginning of the registration and will have the possibility to object to it, and in case of objection the AI system will not be used. The participants will also have the possibility to opt out after the registration and transcription, and in these cases their data will be deleted from the transcript of the meeting. During the meetings a human participant will take notes, so it will be possible to review the transcript generated by AI systems. Personal data included in the transcript will be anonymized in all cases in which anonymization will not negatively affect the purposes of the transcription.

7.3 Other ethical aspects

The project ensures that the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda recommendations that will be developed by WP5 will promote environmental sustainability by advancing frugal AI models that are energy-efficient, incorporating sustainability criteria in AI infrastructure upgrade scenarios, and highlighting green AI applications for environmental benefits.

8 Other Issues

In case of any type of any type of long-term data preservation, collection, usage, or generation of other research outputs of digital nature (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.), these will be stored leveraging project partners research infrastructures, such as SoBigData.

9 References

Reference	
GA	SCIANCE Grant Agreement
European Commission Horizon Europe HE programme guide	https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf
Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template	https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/temp-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx
FAIR Data Guide	https://horizoneuropencpportal.eu/sites/default/files/2022-09/ore-fair-data-guide.pdf
SCIANCE community page Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/communities/sciance/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/
OpenScience CERN Zenodo Page	https://openscience.cern/zenodo
Microsoft SharePoint	https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoft-365/sharepoint/collaboration
Microsoft two-step verification	https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/account-billing/how-to-use-two-step-verification-with-your-microsoft-account-c7910146-672f-01e9-50a0-93b4585e7eb4
OpenAIRE Knowledge Graph	https://graph.openaire.eu/
Living guidelines on the RESPONSIBLE USE OF GENERATIVE AI IN RESEARCH	https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/2b6cf7e5-36ac-41cb-aab5-0d32050143dc_en?filename=ec_rtd_ai-guidelines.pdf
Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI	https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai
SoBigData	https://www.sobigdata.eu/
SoBigData Catalogue	https://pnrr.sobigdata.it/catalogue/
European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity	https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/2b6cf7e5-36ac-41cb-aab5-0d32050143dc_en?filename=ec_rtd_ai-guidelines.pdf